

THE ROLE OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN WORKS OF LOUISA MAY ALCOTT.

Fuzaylova Violetta Borisovna

Bucheon University in Tashkent, Senior Teacher

+99890 903 54 62

Violettafv215@gmail.com

Annotation: The presented article describes the stylistic devices in literary works of L.M.Alcott. The given article analyzes the stylistic devices in: “Little women”, The article illustrates the wide variety of devices that support the literary works with figurative language, that makes the novels more colorful and interesting for the reader.

Key words: stylistic devices, novel, characters, Victorian literature, ideas, female character.

The role of stylistic devices has been one of the most significant parts of all literary works. The function of compositional complexity in literary plot, the wide range of stylistic tools to illustrate characters and events. These stylistic devices support the writers’ ideas and help to discover different themes of writer.

It is important to highlight Victorian literature that closely reveals a vast view of different details that present the criteria of society and time, which make it difficult for the general reader. Victorian literature and the works of many writers fulfilled with general details of lifestyle, including descriptions of domestic settings, culture of aesthetics and clothes. The novel got its peak at 19 centuries. It became more realistic and described problems of people, out of big amount of poetry, the writers used it only at lyrical digression.

The stylistic devices often help to support simplicity of feelings, beauty of language, that are missing the novels of the early time. The author often uses such stylistic devices as metaphor, slimily, hyperbole and the other. It makes the text easier and phonetically more musical.

“Margaret, the eldest of the four, was sixteen, and very pretty, being plump and fair, with large eyes, plenty of soft brown hair, a sweet mouth, and white hands, of which she was rather vain. Fifteen- year – old Jo was very tall, thin, and brown, and reminded one of colts, for she never seemed to know what to do with her long limbs, which were very much in her way. “[1]

Analyzing literary works of Louisa May Alcott “Little women”, we can see many female characters that revealed in unique way of description in the novels. In the novel female characters illustrated with help of four sisters, the writer detached many actions revealed to the plot. The characters questioning and trying to answer in the novel. Each sister possesses her own distinct speaking style. The main character of the novel Jo, she is vibrant and active young girl that faced with difficulties of self -esteem, she faced with the challenges that make her to analyze her life and people around her, it makes reader interested in life of young girls. Her image is not typical for Victorian time. Louisa May Alcott, is using the action verbs in speech of heroes, in order to highlight the active character like Jo in “Little Women”.

“How I wish I was going to college! You do not look as if you liked it”.[2]

The contradictory position of Meg turns the reader to different angle. Being secondary character in the book, her image is strong demonstrate the image of Victorian angel, that been quite popular in her time. She is the eldest siter and writer shows her with help of epithet.

“It is like other people, you know, and I always envy girls who do such things, I am so found of luxury, said Meg, trying to decide which of two shabby gowns was the least shabby”.[3]

Though Jo and Laurie are friend in the book, they do not have much in common. The writer used vivid antithesis to show big contrast for the life attitudes. The novel “Little women” has vivid antithesis that prove the contrasting images: the contrast of wealth and poverty. Jo’s desire for education as the contradiction Laurie’s had no personal motivation to study and work. The striking metaphors in the text capture the mischief of childhood.

“I like his manners, and he looks like a little gentleman, so I have no objection to your knowing him, if a proper opportunity comes. He brought the flowers himself, and I should have asked him in, if I had been sure what was going on upstairs. He looked so wistful as he went away, hearing the frolic and evidently having none of his own”. [4]

The same approach can be found in another works such as “An old-fashioned girl”. In the novel reader can see contrast of class inequality. In this literary work L.M. Alcott introduce two new characters, young girls Polly and Fanny, so opposite in everything that is only possible. For the main character Funny neatness is important, she presents the image of ideal girl in contradiction to visual image high manners writer shows countryside girl Polly, she is lack of manner but her inner world is fulfilled with good character and tender soul.

“I will try to take things as the come, and make the best of them”.[5]

Another novel that completely different by its look on people images and novel that shows psychological depth that gripped the attention of reader until the last word, is “Behind the mask, or a Woman’s power” the writer using many details to depict the image of Jean Muir, deceptive person that practice with manipulation.

“The curtain is down , so I may be myself for a few hours”.[6]

In conclusion, Loisa May Olcott used uncommon style, by blending realism novels with elements of romanticism, by adding stylistic devices. The figurative language that helped her to move from the standards of her time novel. Her characters are full of psychological challenges that makes it interesting out of the written time. The novels that filled with devices are not only moving the reader from the simple critical opinion about problems it helps to deep understanding of human soul, feeling, and shows the necessity of analysis in life of people.

The list of used literature:

1. Little Women / L. Alcott. Moscow: AST Publishing House, 2022. p. 5.
2. Little Women / L. Alcott. Moscow: AST Publishing House, 2022. p. 24.
3. Little Women / L. Alcott. Moscow: AST Publishing House, 2022. p. 20.
4. Little Women / L. Alcott. Moscow: AST Publishing House, 2022. p. 19.
5. An Old-Fashioned Girl. Boston: Robert Brothers, 1870. p. 187.

6. Behind a Mask, or A Woman's Power. London, 1866. p. 8.